

Abstract

Acupuncture Effect on Reaction-Time Changes in Parkinson's Disease Patients – Case Study Series.

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Abstract

Background: Parkinson's Disease (PD) is a progressive neurodegenerative condition associated with deficits in reaction time. These delays can lead to falls, resulting in limited independence, diminished quality of life, higher rates of institutionalisation, and increased healthcare costs. This study aimed to examine the effects of an acupuncture protocol on motor time response following an auditory stimulus.

Methods: This study employed a case series design. Reaction times to both rhythmic and random auditory stimuli were evaluated at six different intervals over a month-long acupuncture treatment protocol using the Biopac MP36 system.

Results: A tendency for more pronounced improvements in response time was observed on the side of the body more affected by the disease compared to the contralateral side. Patients generally showed better response values to random auditory stimuli than to rhythmic ones. Additionally, there was a noticeable trend towards improved results when considering the cumulative effects of the acupuncture protocol.

Conclusions: Our findings indicate that reaction time may serve as a sensitive and useful tool for motor function assessment in PD patients. Furthermore, the results suggest that the acupuncture protocol used may improve the efficacy of motor responses following both random and rhythmic stimuli. A tendency for higher acupuncture efficacy in random stimuli responses was found during the early stages of the disease. However, further in-depth research with a larger participant pool and statistical evaluation is necessary to validate these promising results.

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